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European Centre for the Development
of Vocational Training

Stemming the tide of teacher shortages in Europe

Supporting VET teachers' professional development

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Teacher shortages: an EU-wide fact

Dramatic increase
in some countries
and in remote and
disadvantage areas

Vary across subjects
and sectors:
**severe in STEM,
foreign languages,
informatics**

Lack of qualified
teachers across EU
- associated with a
**decline in student
performance**

**High in
EU policy
agenda**

Source: [Unesco, 2024](#); [E&T monitor, 2023](#) and [2024](#); [EENEE-NESET Analytical Report, 1/2023](#); [Cedefop, 2022](#)

What causes teacher shortages?

- ① An **ageing** teaching force
- ② **Higher demand** for specific skills
- ③ Lack of **attractiveness** to the teaching profession
- ④ Accelerated **teacher absenteeism & turnover**

Rethinking teaching careers

COMPLEXITY OF TEACHING PROFESSION

- Not fully prepared at early career stages
- Limited CPD and career advancement opportunities

CHALLENGING WORKING ENVIRONMENTS

- High workloads & stress
- Overcrowded classrooms
- Harassment and violence

Source: [Cedefop pilot survey of VET teachers, 2022](#), [Cedefop ESJS2, 2021](#)

High teacher recruitment difficulty

Teaching professionals

Sources: ESJS2 and Skills forecast

As a result...

Teaching is not a first career choice

- Only for **67% of teachers**, teaching was their primary career choice
- In some countries, few graduates from teacher training programmes take a job in a school

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VET teachers: more likely to be looking for another job

Making teaching careers attractive

1

Improve societal appreciation of teachers

Only **17.7%** of teachers across EU countries believe that their profession is valued

Source: [Unesco, 2024](#); [E&T monitor, 2023](#) and [Cedefop, 2022](#)

Making teaching careers attractive

2

Raise salaries

10.5% lower

compared to tertiary-educated workers

Only 40% of VET teachers

on average are satisfied with their salary

Source: [E&T monitor, 2024](#) and [OECD, 2021](#)

Making teaching careers attractive

3 Increase job and career stability

VET teachers are more likely to have a **temporary contract** than general education teachers

Source: [OECD, 2021](#), [Cedefop pilot survey of VET teachers, 2022](#)

Supporting teachers' professional development

4

Lift barriers to high quality CPD

- CPD is obligatory in most MS but in only few leads to career progression
- Only few MS conduct systematic teachers' needs assessment to design CPD

Source: [Cedefop, 2022](#), [Cedefop pilot survey of VET teachers, 2022](#)

EVTS main objective

By collecting data from across the EU, the survey aims to **inform better policies** that reflect the realities of the profession and provide the support needed to help IVET teachers thrive.

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EVTS EUROPEAN VOCATIONAL
TEACHER SURVEY

Addressing their needs is key to helping them in their multifaceted role.

EVTS campaign #MoreThanTeaching

What is the EVTS?

The European Vocational Teacher Survey (EVTS) is an important social survey conducted on behalf of Cedefop, and EU agency.

The EVTS is Europe's first major survey dedicated to understanding the skill gaps, professional development and working conditions of teachers in vocational education and training (VET) schools.

How does it work?

Who can participate?

Randomly selected teachers who teach vocational or general education subjects for students at initial VET schools.

How?

You will receive an invitation email with a number and password to log in and complete the survey.

When?

You can participate between October 2025 and June 2026.

How long does it take?

It takes 30 minutes to complete the online survey.

Why participate?

Influence policy

Your responses will help inform better national and European policies for the teaching profession in VET that will, among others, prepare VET teachers for major social challenges, such as AI, climate change and social exclusion.

Engagement opportunities

Gain exclusive access to online events, network with other teachers, and share best practices.

Recognition

Receive a personalized certificate of participation from Cedefop.

Monetary incentives

To reward participating schools, we additionally offer vouchers for schools to buy equipment.

Make your voice heard!

By taking part, you contribute to **vital research** that will benefit teachers

Contact information?

For more information, visit the EVTS website at <https://www.evts2025.eu>

Who is conducting the research?

The European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training (Cedefop) is an EU agency that supports the promotion, development and implementation of the Union policy in the field of vocational education and training (VET) as well as skills and qualifications policies by working together with the European Commission, Member States and social partners.

The survey is carried with the support of Verian (Verian Group Belgium SA) - an independent research, evidence, evaluation, and communications agency.

Welcome, VET Teachers to the European Vocational Teacher Survey!

[Click here to login and complete the survey](#)

Your participation in the European Vocational Teacher Survey (EVTS) is critical to improving vocational education and training across Europe. This section provides all the information you need to contribute effectively and understand the impact of your involvement.

Why Participate?

As a VET teacher, your insights are invaluable. Your responses, along with those of thousands of VET teachers across the EU, will provide valuable evidence to improve policies aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of continuing professional development (CPD) of teachers in initial VET schools within EU Members States. The survey results will inform strategies aimed at enhancing professional development opportunities, improving teaching practices, and supporting your growth as an educator.

> **Influence policy:** Your responses will contribute to the development of national and European policies that support the continuing professional development of VET teachers. [Read more...](#)

Join us in EVTS official launch

European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training

SHAPING LEARNING AND SKILLS FOR EUROPE **30** YEARS

Fourth Policy learning forum

Launching the European Vocational Teacher Survey (EVTS)

25-26 September 2025
Hybrid event

#VETTeachersTrainers
#VETtoolkit

If your school has been chosen to be part of this initiative

Participate in the EVTS to voice what works—and what can be improved!

#MoreThanTeaching

A close-up photograph of a person's hand resting on a laptop keyboard, with the keys slightly blurred. The hand is positioned on the left side of the frame, with fingers spread across the keyboard. The background is a soft, out-of-focus grey.

Knowledge hub for VET teachers

VET toolkit for tackling early leaving

www.cedefop.europa.eu/TEL-toolkit

VET toolkit for empowering NEETs

<https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/tools/neets>

VET toolkit for tackling early leaving

Source of support to policy makers and education and training providers

Introduction

Identify

Intervene

Evaluate

Resources

Ambassadors

Advanced search

Ambassadors tackling early leaving from VET

BECOME AN
AMBASSADOR

Dr Giovanni Crisonà

cscs.it / skillman.eu

 Italy

Thank you

www.cedefop.europa.eu

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